

Dynamo

Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation
of Light by Phononic Architectures.

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D1.4 Algorithm for the density of modes

Date: 3 September 2024

D.1.4: Algorithm for the density of modes

WP1. T.1.4: Design of the algorithm for the computation of the
density of modes

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe
research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046489.

1. Version History

Version	Date	Beneficiary	Author
V1	30/08/2024	Imperial College London	Marc Martí-Sabaté, Benjamin Vial, Richard Wiltshaw, Sébastien Guenneau, Richard Craster, Daniel Torrent
	Date	Beneficiary	Reviewed and approved by
V2	03/09/2024	UJI, CNRS	Daniel Torrent, Sébastien Guenneau

Dynamo D1.4: Algorithm for the density of modes

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046489.

2. Technical References

Project Number	101046489
Project Acronym	Dynamo
Project Title	Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation of Light by Phononic Architectures
Granting Authority	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
Call	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01
Topic	HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01
Type of the Action	HORIZON EIC Grants
Duration	1 March 2022 - 28 February 2026 (48 months)
Entry into force of the Grant	1 March 2022
Project Coordinator	Daniel Torrent Martí

Deliverable No.	D1.4
Work Package	WP1 – Modelling of phononic surfaces
Task	T1.4. - Design of the algorithm for the computation of the density of modes
Dissemination level*	PU - Public
Lead beneficiary	IMPERIAL COLLEGE LONDON
PIC of the Lead beneficiary	999844573
Due date of deliverable	31 08 2024
Actual submission date	03 09 2024

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046489.

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3. Introduction

3.1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the goal and scope of the work carried out in WP1, mainly in relation to task T1.4. Following the scope of task T1.4, its main assumptions rely on developing new analytical and numerical tools for the modelling of phononic surfaces. We address two aspects of the modelling framework – theoretical and computational. The main focus of the theoretical part is on developing the equations for the computation of the local density of states (LDOS) directly from the scattering problem or by means of the quasi-normal modal expansion (QNMs). In the numerical part, we will give two examples and compare the accuracy of the computations following both methods. The deliverable is formulated as follows:

D1.4: Algorithm for the density of modes.

The above-mentioned goals of the deliverable were achieved through the realization of the following tasks:

- Developing the multiple scattering formulation for mass-spring resonators on top of a thin elastic plate
- Defining the nonlinear eigenvalue problem and finding the suitable optimisation algorithm for the numerical solution of the problem
- Expressing the scattering problem as a superposition of the eigenmodes of the system (QNMs),
- performing numerical analyses,
- analysis and selection of key parameters.

3.2. Relation to Other Project Documents

This document refers to the report on deliverables D1.2 and D1.3.

3.3. Reference Documents

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4. Theoretical framework

We consider a thin elastic plate of thickness h , mass density ρ , Young's modulus E , Poisson ratio ν and loaded with a finite distribution of N mass-spring resonators each with force constant k_{R_α} and mass m_{R_α} , located at positions R_α . According to Kirchoff-Love theory, the governing equation of motion for the plate's displacement W in a time-harmonic regime $\exp(-i\omega t)$ is given by [1]:

$$P(\omega)W(r) = (\nabla^4 - k^4 - R(\omega))W(r) = 0$$

Where we define the biharmonic operator $\nabla^4 = (\nabla \cdot \nabla)^2$, the wave number k satisfying $k^4 = \omega^2 \rho h / D$, the plate bending stiffness $D = Eh^3 / 12(1 - \nu^2)$ and the operator $R(\omega)$ defined as:

$$R(\omega)W(r) = \sum_{\alpha} t_{\alpha}(\omega)W(R_{\alpha})\delta(r - R_{\alpha})$$

The quantities t_{α} are the resonators' strength or impedance [2]:

$$t_{\alpha}(\omega) = \frac{m_{R_{\alpha}}}{D} \frac{\omega_{R_{\alpha}}^2 \omega^2}{\omega_{R_{\alpha}}^2 - \omega^2}$$

With $\omega_{R_{\alpha}} = \sqrt{k_{R_{\alpha}}/m_{R_{\alpha}}}$ the resonant frequencies.

Solving the first equation is achieved by first finding the Green's function of the plate without resonators satisfying

$$(\nabla^4 - k^4)G(r) = \delta(r)$$

The solution is known explicitly [3] as:

$$G(r) = \frac{i}{8k^2} [H_0(kr) - H_0(ikr)]$$

Where H_0 is the zeroth-order Hankel function of the first kind.

4.1. Multiple scattering for flexural waves in thin elastic plates

For an incident excitation $W^i(r)$, the multiple scattering problem is solved by a linear superposition of the incident and scattered fields as follows:

$$W(r) = W^i(r) + \sum_{\alpha} \phi_{\alpha} G(r - R_{\alpha})$$

Here we utilize Foldy's method [4,5] and express the solution in terms of the "external" field $\phi_{\alpha} = T_{\alpha}(\omega)\psi^e(R_{\alpha})$, where $\psi^e(R_{\alpha})$ is simply the total field minus the contribution of the α scatterer, and the coefficients T_{α} are given

$$T_{\alpha} = \frac{t_{\alpha}}{1 - it_{\alpha}/(8k^2)}$$

The multiple scattering problem is solved by considering the following system of equations

$$M\Phi = \Psi^i$$

With the elements of the matrix given by $M_{\alpha\beta} = \delta_{\alpha\beta} t_{\alpha}^{-1} - G(R_{\alpha} - R_{\beta})$ and the right hand side is a vector containing the values of the incident field at the resonators' positions $\Psi_{\alpha}^i = W^i(R_{\alpha})$. The standard approach is to invert the matrix M to get the scattered field,

however this can be inefficient for large arrays, lacks physical insight and is not well suited to optimisation techniques all of which are addressed by the QNM methodology.

4.2. Nonlinear eigenvalue problem

The philosophy behind QNM is that we first identify the eigenstates of the cluster; these form the fundamental states of the system and therefore are an ideal basis in which to couch the solution and incoming field. The complication is finding the QNMs via the efficient and accurate identification of the eigenstates. We proceed by seeking solutions of the governing equations without excitation, hence setting $W^i = 0$. One needs to find the eigenfrequencies ω_n and eigenvectors Φ_n satisfying:

$$M(\omega_n)\Phi_n = 0$$

This defines a nonlinear eigenvalue problem and one way to solve it is by searching for the zeros of the determinant of M :

$$\det\{M(\omega_n)\} = 0$$

There are various methods to solve this problem, that broadly separate into two families: contour integral techniques [6-8] or iterative methods [9]. Each approach has advantages and disadvantages; contour integral methods compute all singularities within a given region of the complex plane but are usually costly as they demand the accurate evaluation of integrals along a possibly large closed path, although iterative methods are faster they require an initial guess and can sometimes miss solutions. Here we use a variant of the latter, namely Newton's method with a generalized Rayleigh quotient iteration [10-12] to find the eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

4.3. Quasinormal modal expansion

According to Keldyřh theorem [13], we have:

$$M^{-1}(\omega) = \sum_n \frac{1}{\omega - \omega_n} \frac{\Phi_n^{L*} \Phi_n^T}{\Phi_n \cdot M'(\omega_n) \Phi_n} + h(\omega)$$

Where prime quantities denote derivatives with respect to ω , and $h(\omega)$ is an analytic function representing the non-resonant background which is zero if M is a strictly proper rational function [8]. In general, it is also necessary to consider the left eigenvectors, Φ_n^L , satisfying $\Phi_n^{L T} M(\omega_n) = 0$. It is worth noting that the Rayleigh quotient [11,12] method computes both the left and right eigenvectors to iterate towards the eigenvalue. Typically, however, Φ_n^L is related to the right eigenvectors of $M^\dagger(\omega_n)\Phi_n^L = 0$,

where $M^\dagger = (M^T)^*$ is the Hermitian transpose of M associated with the adjoint operator and we define superscript T and $*$ by the transpose and complex conjugate respectively. Since M is symmetric, $M^\dagger = M^*$, and the left eigenvectors are simply the complex conjugate transpose of the right eigenvectors Φ_n .

However, the previous expansion is not unique as the system is overcomplete. Neglecting the non-resonant terms and following [14], we take a generalisation of the previous theorem and write the expansion for the solution Φ

$$\Phi = \sum_n \frac{u(\omega_n)}{u(\omega)} \frac{1}{\omega - \omega_n} \frac{\Phi_n \cdot \Psi^i}{\Phi_n \cdot M'(\omega_n) \Phi_n} \Phi_n = \sum_n b_n(\omega) \Phi_n$$

Where we assumed that the modes have been normalized such that $\langle \Phi_n, \Phi_n \rangle_M = 1$. In

the case of polynomial or rational eigenproblems, it has been shown in [13] that u is a polynomial of maximum degree depending on the dispersive properties; the situation is more complicated here as we use the Green's function formalism involving transcendental functions and hence the eigenvalue problem is now nonlinear. For the cases tested numerically it seems that $u = 1/k^3$ works optimally, and we will use this in the examples below.

4.4. Green's function and local density of states

In particular, the previous equation gives the Green's function $g(\omega, r, r')$ solution of a forced problem with a point source located at r' in terms of eigenvalues and eigenvectors:

$$g(\omega, r, r') = G(\omega, r - r') + \sum_n \left[\frac{u(\omega_n)}{u(\omega)} \frac{1}{\omega - \omega_n} \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \Phi_{n, \alpha} \Phi_{n, \beta} G(\omega, r - R_\alpha) G(\omega, r' - R_\beta) \right]$$

The local density of states (LDOS) is therefore expanded as [14]:

$$L(\omega, r) = \frac{4k^3}{\pi} \text{Im}[g(\omega, r, r)] = L_0(\omega) + \frac{4k^3}{\pi} \sum_n \text{Im} \left[\frac{u(\omega_n)}{u(\omega)} \frac{1}{\omega - \omega_n} \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \Phi_{n, \alpha} \Phi_{n, \beta} G(\omega, r - R_\alpha) G(\omega, r - R_\beta) \right]$$

Where $L_0(\omega) = k/2\pi$ is the LDOS of the bare plate.

4.3. Far-field radiation

The far field from a source at $R_\alpha = (R_\alpha, \theta_\alpha)$ is

$$G(r - R_\alpha) \sim G(r) e^{-ikR_\alpha \cos\theta \cos(\theta - \theta_\alpha)}$$

This approximation holds for all cylindrically outgoing scattered waves as a direct consequence of satisfying the Sommerfeld radiation condition at infinity. The far-field response depends only on the large argument approximation of $H_0^{(1)}(r)$. The scattered far field of the cluster follows as

$$W^S(r) \sim G(r) f(\theta)$$

With the far-field radiation function

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N \phi_\beta e^{-ikR_\beta \cos\theta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}$$

Replacing the expression for the scattering coefficients given by Keldyř theorem, we obtain

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N \sum_n b_n(\omega) \phi_{n\beta} e^{-ikR_\beta \cos\theta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}$$

The far-field radiation function for a given QNM of the cluster is given by

$$\hat{f}_n(\theta) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N \phi_{n\beta} e^{-ik_n R_\beta \cos\theta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}$$

Defining

$$f_n(\theta) = \sum_{\beta=1}^N \phi_{n\beta} e^{-ikR_\beta \cos\theta \cos(\theta - \theta_\beta)}$$

We have $f(\theta) = \sum_n b_n(\omega) f_n(\theta)$ so the scattering cross section is

$$\sigma^s = \frac{1}{16\pi D k^2} \int_0^{2\pi} |f(\theta)|^2 d\theta = \frac{|\Phi|^2}{8Dk^2} \sum_n \sum_m \text{Re} \left[b_n(\omega) b_m^*(\omega) \sigma_{nm}^s \right]$$

With

$$\sigma_{nm}^s = \frac{\Phi_n \cdot \Phi_m^*}{8Dk^2}$$

And the extinction cross section is

$$\sigma^e = \text{Im} f(0) = \sum_n \text{Im} \left[b_n(\omega) F_n(0) \right] = \sum_n \text{Re} \left[b_n(\omega) \right] \text{Re} \left[\sigma_n^e \right] + \text{Im} \left[b_n(\omega) \right] \text{Im} \left[\sigma_n^e \right]$$

With $\sigma_n^e = i \sum_{\beta} \Phi_{n,\beta}^* e^{ik_n R_{\beta} \cos \cos(\theta - \theta_{\beta})}$. The resonators can potentially have damping by considering a complex valued resonant frequency ω_r , then the absorption cross section is non-null and given by

$$\sigma^a = \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[t_{\alpha}(\omega)] |\Phi|^2 = \sum_n \sum_m \text{Re} \left[b_n(\omega) b_m^*(\omega) \sigma_{nm}^a \right]$$

With

$$\sigma_{nm}^a = \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[t_{\alpha}(\omega)] \Phi_n \cdot \Phi_m^*$$

For a unit amplitude incident plane wave propagating in the direction $\theta = 0$, the radiation pattern function satisfies the optical theorem

$$\sigma^e = \sigma^s + \sigma^a$$

5. Numerical results

5.1. Quasicrystals: Penrose tilings

The LDOS function characterizes the behavior of sources placed inside an array or a finite cluster, and are measures of the density of the spectrum. It is simple to understand physically, as it is proportional to the total power radiated by a source through the structure. There has been extensive studies on LDOS for both periodic and finite arrays in photonics, acoustics and elasticity, with detailed analysis of the underlying mechanisms of enhancement or suppression of emission. Especially, in quasicrystals, where the analysis behind the emergence of localized modes and band gaps are increasingly popular concepts to exploit. However, computing LDOS maps are often expensive as one has to solve the scattering problem at each frequency and for each point of the spatial discretization. In contrast, the QNMs expansion formula allows for a fast approximation of spatially and spectrally resolved LDOS once the eigenmodes and eigenfrequencies have been found.

As an example of a quasicrystal we consider a set of 191 identical resonators arranged on a Penrose lattice, with mass m_p and stiffness $k_p = \omega_p^2 m_p$ (these results can be found in [15]). The normalized LDOS at the centre of the gap is computed as a function of frequency and displayed in Fig. (1) (bottom part) by multiple scattering (blue line) and the QNM expansion (dashed red line), showing excellent agreement except for the lower frequencies; however, these correspond to a pseudo band gap where the resonant response is less important. This discrepancy may be reconciled by taking more modes into account in the expansion. This highlights the excitation of a QNM with a

high quality factor at $\omega = 1.208\omega_p$ and a large field at the centre, leading to a strong LDOS enhancement of about 3 orders of magnitude compared to its value for the empty plate. A second resonance occurs at $\omega = 1.213\omega_p$. The LDOS maps corresponding to these frequencies are shown in Fig. (2), and the agreement of our method compared to the solution of the scattering problem is striking (see the error maps in right panels of Fig. (2)) and is done at a fraction of the computational cost once the eigenproblem is solved. Interestingly, the map distribution at Fig. (2) (b) retains the five-fold rotational symmetry of the structure, which is linked to the fact that Penrose tilings are obtained from two-dimensional projections from a five-dimensional cubic structure using the cut and project method. The numerically efficient calculation of density of states functions paves the way for manipulation and shaping near field.

Fig. 1: Resonant enhancement of the LDOS in quasicrystals. Top: spectrum of the structure. Bottom: LDOS normalized to its value for the bare plate at the centre of the cluster as a function of frequency obtained by multiple scattering (solid blue line) and the QNM expansion (dashed red line)

Fig. 2: Normalized LDOS maps $2\pi L(r)/k$ computed by QNM expansion (left) and error $2\pi|L(r) - L^{ref}(r)|/k$ with respect to the reference map computed with multipole scattering (right) at frequencies (a) $\omega = 1.208\omega_p$ and (b) $\omega = 1.213\omega_p$.

5.2. Twisted bilayers

As a second example, we examine the local density of states (LDOS) of a twisted bilayer structure. Twisted bilayers are superpositions of two periodic lattices rotated one respect to the other by a given angle. In our case, we have set a cluster of two square lattices with an angle of rotation $\theta = 22^\circ$. The circular cluster is set to have a radius of 5 times the lattice parameter of the original lattice. All the resonators have the same properties ($\gamma_0 = 200$, $\omega_r = 20\pi$). The complex frequency spectrum is depicted in Fig. (3).

Fig. 3: Complex spectrum for a square lattice twisted bilayer cluster with $R_{max} = 5a$ and $\theta = 22^\circ$. The map shows the $|\omega_n|$, and superimposed to the map, the blue points are the eigenfrequencies found by using the generalized Rayleigh quotient nonlinear solver. In the low frequency regime, we can see a big density of modes, while a pair of eigenfrequencies are located near $\Omega \approx 5$.

The spectrum of the twisted bilayer structure shows a big density of modes in the low frequency regime, while a few modes at high frequency. This behaviour was observed in [16], where only the real part of the frequency was analysed. The phase portrait of the eigenvalue will give us similar information (Fig. (4)):

Fig. 4: Phase portrait for the determinant of the M matrix for the square lattice twisted bilayer cluster.

Other than the low frequency high quality factor modes, and the high frequency high quality factor pair of eigenfrequencies, we also have a series of possible eigenfrequencies with low quality factor (big imaginary frequency part). These are characterized in the phase portrait by the fork-like structure. They have not been spotted by the nonlinear solver. Since these eigenfrequencies are low quality factor, they will have influence over a wide range of frequencies, but their contribution to the density of states will be minimal.

Fig. 5: Eigenmodes corresponding to the two highest eigenfrequencies found for the square lattice twisted bilayer structure. Both resonances have the same real frequency, but they slightly differ in their imaginary frequency term.

Figure (5) shows two of the eigenstates found for the twisted bilayer structure. They are the pair of high frequency resonances that are isolated from the rest of the spectrum. The real frequency is the same for both, but the imaginary part is slightly different. In the Appendix the rest of eigenmodes can be found. The LDOS of the structure can be computed as a function of frequency. Fig. (6).

Fig. 6: LDOS of the cluster at the frequency corresponding to the real part of the highest eigenfrequencies.

The matching between the direct computation (left) and the modal computation (right) is reasonably good. Only the magnitude of the peaks differs, but the main features are shared between both computations. The differences might be because our QNM expansion has skipped the low-quality factor resonances of the system. The computation of the LDOS for the rest of frequencies in the system can be seen in the Appendix. It is noticeable that for some frequencies the agreement between direct and modal is not so good. Nonetheless, the main features of the LDOS are equally computed by both methods, and the differences are due to this low quality factor resonances that have been kept.

6. Conclusions

In the study reported, we have set the theoretical framework for the expansion of the scattering field of a finite cluster of mass-spring resonators on top of a thin elastic plate as a modal expansion in terms of the quasi-normal modes from the cluster. This expansion paves the way to a more efficient computation for the classical analysis in scattering problems (scattered field, LDOS, far-field radiation and scattering cross-section). The efficiency of this method with respect to direct computation scales with the number of resonators in the system. Thus, it is optimal for the computation of scattering problems with a big number of scatterers. Notwithstanding, the QNMs expansion requires the computation of the eigenfrequencies and eigenstates of the cluster, which can be computationally expensive when the number of resonators increases.

7. Appendix

- Eigenfrequencies of the twisted bilayer structure

Fig. 8: Eigenmodes of the square lattice twisted bilayer structure.

- LDOS for the twisted bilayer structure

Fig. 8: LDOS computed at the real frequency of the different eigenfrequencies of the cluster. The left panels are direct computations, while the right panels have been computed using the QNM expansion.